

Delivery 2.5

Report on the summer schools

Version 1

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

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D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

1. Executive Summary

As part of GRINNAQUA's mission to strengthen the consortium's scientific capacity in aquaculture, two advanced Summer Schools, focusing on key technologies in genetic improvement and fish health were successfully delivered. The first, held at the University of Edinburgh (UEDIN), provided in-depth training on genomic and genetic tools to enhance disease resistance and performance in aquaculture stocks. The second, hosted by INIA-CSIC, in Madrid, focused on the application of flow cytometry for analysing immune cell populations in aquatic species.

Each four-day program combined lectures with practical sessions and was attended by early-career researchers, and PhD students from the partner institutions and the broader aquaculture research community. The events supported skill development, encouraged scientific exchange, and reinforced collaboration across the GRINNAQUA consortium. This report outlines the activities conducted, participant engagement, and the main outcomes achieved during both Summer Schools.

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

Content

1. Executive Summary	3
2. Introduction	5
3. Summer school: Genomic and genetic tools for the blue revolution	5
4. Summer school: Application of flow cytometry to study immune responses in fish	10
5. Document Information.....	16

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

2. Introduction

This document compiles the outcomes of the two GRINNAQUA Summer Schools held at Roslin Institute – University of Edinburgh (Edinburgh, UK) and INIA-CSIC (Madrid, Spain), which were designed to address critical areas of innovation in aquaculture research. Focusing respectively on genetic technologies and flow cytometry, the training programs aimed to provide participants with both theoretical foundations and hands-on experience using advanced tools relevant to stock improvement and fish immunology. The Summer Schools brought together participants from GRINNAQUA partner institutions and external PhD students, fostering knowledge transfer, practical skill-building, and cross-institutional collaboration. The following sections detail the structure, participation, and impact of each event.

3. Summer school: Genomic and genetic tools for the blue revolution

The first GRINNAQUA summer school (Fig.1) was hosted and organized by the partners at the Roslin Institute / University of Edinburgh and supported by the team at CIIMAR. The event, focusing on “Genomic and genetic tools for the blue revolution” was a 4-day event, spanning between the 2nd and 5th of July 2024.

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

Fig. 1: Agenda of the GRINNAQUA summer school 2024

The training opportunity was initially planned for 14 participants, 12 within the GRINNAQUA consortium and three grants for participants outside the consortium, as an opportunity to

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

expand the partners' network. These grants covered travel and accommodation and a public open call was open and disseminated on social media, the project website and through the [April 2024 GRINNAQUA newsletter](#). Applicants were selected based on their background and the summer school usefulness for their current and future work (Fig. 3). We received 36 applications (Fig. 2) and PhD students were considered a priority. An additional spot was opened for a PhD student within the EU project cluster GRINNAQUA is a part of, strengthening the connection between the projects. This extra spot was attributed to a student within [Cure4Aqua](#).

grinnaqua

Call for participants
Practical and theoretical portions

Grinnaqua is offering **3 grants** to help cover travel and accommodation expenses, for those who want to participate in the 4-day summer school.

Participants will be selected based on:

- Their degree (priority will be given to PhD students)
- Letter of support from the supervisor
- The topic of their thesis or their current work (for non PhD students)
- How useful this training will be for their current and future work (preference will be given to those who will apply these skills in the near future)

Grants will be offered to the 3 applicants that better fit the criteria

Fig. 2: Announcement of the open call for travel and accommodation grants to attend the 2024 GRINNAQUA summer school

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

Fig. 3: Background of applicants for a grant in the grinnaqua summer school 2024.

Out of the 15 participants (Fig. 4), 9 provided anonymous feedback on the event quality and fit to their expectations.

Fig. 4: Participants and teachers in the 2024 GRINNAQUA summer school, at the Roslin Institute, Edinburgh, UK.

Overall, participants were very pleased and considered the quality of the summer school as very high, particularly in terms of its duration, the support material provided and the overall usefulness of the newly acquired skills (Fig. 5).

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

Fig. 5: Participants' feedback on the summer school content, duration, material provided and usefulness, where 1 is "strongly disagree" and 5 is "strongly agree"

Participants were also very pleased with the teachers' ability to convey the subjects (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6: Participants feedback on the teachers' proficiency and capacity to communicate the content, where 1 is "strongly disagree" and 5 is "strongly agree"

Our efforts to ensure everyone was comfortable and able to find food fitting to their needs was also recognized by the participants (Fig. 7)

Fig. 7: Participants feedback on the venue and dietary options, where 1 is "strongly disagree" and 5 is "strongly agree"

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

The open question where participants could offer suggestions to improve our workshops was met with really nice and supportive messages:

- “Nothing at all, that was a really great experience!! Thank you.”
- “The organizers did an excellent job in arranging a highly engaging and productive workshop. The lectures were captivating, and the hands-on laboratory activities were interactive and will be useful for future practice.”

The summer school agenda, profile of the teachers, and learning materials, which the teachers were kind enough to make publicly available, can be found on the [GRINNAQUA website](#). The availability of these learning materials was disseminated through social media and in the [October 2024 GRINNAQUA newsletter](#).

4. Summer school: Application of flow cytometry to study immune responses in fish

The second GRINNAQUA summer school (Fig. 8) was hosted and organized by the partners at INIA/CSIC and supported by the team at CIIMAR. The event, focusing on “Application of flow cytometry to study immune responses in fish” was a 4-day event, spanning between the 9th and 12th of June 2025.

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

The poster features a central grid background with the 'grinn aqua' logo in teal and blue. Surrounding the logo are several icons: a microscope, a test tube with a magnifying glass, a lightbulb, a notebook with a pencil, a syringe, and a fish. The text is centered and includes the event title, dates, and location. At the bottom, there is a row of logos for funding and partner organizations.

grinn aqua

green innovation strategies for animal health management: towards sustainable aquaculture

SUMMER SCHOOL

Application of flow cytometry to study immune responses in fish

9 to 12 June 2025
INIA-CSIC, Madrid, Spain

Co-funded by the European Union GA 101079467

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D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

Fig. 8: Agenda of the GRINNAQUA summer school 2025

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

The training opportunity was planned for 12 participants, due to logistic limitations. All partners within the GRINNAQUA consortium were interested in having their students participating in the summer school. For this reason no grants were opened and the slots were filled by the GRINNAQUA team: 6 participants from CIIMAR, 2 from UiB, 2 from UEDIN and 2 from INIA-CSIC (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9: Participants and teachers in the 2025 GRINNAQUA summer school, at INIA, Madrid, Spain.

Out of the 12 participants, 7 provided anonymous feedback on the event quality and fit to their expectations

Overall, participants were very pleased and considered the quality of the summer school as very high, particularly in terms of its duration, the support material provided and the overall usefulness of the newly acquired skills (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10: Participants' feedback on the summer school content, duration, material provided and usefulness, where 1 is "strongly disagree" and 5 is "strongly agree"

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

Participants were also very pleased with the teachers' ability to convey the subjects (Fig. 11)

Fig. 11: Participants feedback on the teachers' proficiency and capacity to communicate the content, where 1 is "strongly disagree" and 5 is "strongly agree"

Our efforts to ensure everyone was comfortable and able to find food fitting to their needs was also recognized by the participants (Fig. 12)

Fig. 12: Participants feedback on the venue and dietary options, where 1 is "strongly disagree" and 5 is "strongly agree"

The open question where participants could offer suggestions to improve our workshops, "Do you have any suggestions or comments for the organizers?", was met with very constructive suggestions:

- "Extend the workshop by half a day to spend time on data analysis"
- "Perhaps more computers for the final analysis (we only had one) of the data acquired during the workshop."

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

The summer school agenda and profile of the teachers can be found on the [GRINNAQUA website](#). Unfortunately, the teachers were not comfortable with sharing their presentations as they included some sensitive information.

D2.5 - Report on the summer schools

5. Document Information

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Authors	Tânia Pereira
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